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D5.7 - Final Report on legal and organisational regulations for EPOS-Private Sector Interactions

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1. Introduction

According to the grant agreement no 871121 — EPOS SP, the purpose of task 5.3. is to develop the legal and organisational setting for EPOS-private sector cooperation. The work carried out in Task 5.3 has been divided into 3 phases, at the end of which the following deliverables are submitted:

- Deliverable **D5.5 Overview of the legal regulations for EPOS-Private Sector collaboration;**
- Deliverable **D5.6 First Report on legal and organizational regulations for EPOS-Private Sector interactions;**
- Deliverable **D5.7 Final Report on legal and organizational regulations for EPOS-Private Sector interactions.**

As part of the work on Deliverable D5.5 Overview of legal regulations for EPOS-Private Sector collaboration, research was carried out to describe the preliminary conditions of Research Infrastructures integrated under EPOS, important for defining the legal framework for cooperation with the private sector (further on also as “PS”). The research was based on data obtained from interviews with people responsible for pilot projects developed under Task 5.1.

The main conclusions from the analysis of the data and information collected during the work on Deliverable D5.5 were as follows:

- I. **Ownership rights** to the Research Infrastructure integrated under EPOS belong to the institutional members of individual TCS.
- II. The members also own **the know-how** that may be essential to the private sector, and necessary to offer services and cooperate.
- III. The member organisations participating in the pilot projects expect to have **DIRECT** relations with the private sector.
- IV. The important role of EPOS ERIC in the relation with the private sector may be that of the **brokering institution**.
- V. Considerable part of the services developed within the pilot projects are either **not designed to propose a direct service offer** to the private sector or are not yet mature enough to prepare the identifiable offer.

Based on this conclusion it was decided that the work on task 5.3 should cover two major issues:

1. **Defining relevant actions that may be undertaken on the level of EPOS ERIC**

In this framework, the important area was to analyse the role of EPOS ERIC as a **brokering institution**, that is to name main objectives of EPOS ERIC acting in this capacity, discuss potential tools to achieve it and analyse how EPOS ERIC activities as a brokering institution may influence creation of relevant legal framework for cooperation with private sector. The activities of the brokering institution can significantly influence the feasibility and design of the legal framework, and are crucial for promoting the kind of collaboration with the private sector that would result in innovation. As a result of further discussions at meetings and panels organised (or co-organised) in the framework of Task 5.3, it was also possible to define other activities relevant to the perspective of relations with the private sector that should be initiated at the EPOS ERIC level.

The outcome of that work is described in Chapter 3 hereof.

2. Descriptions of existing and potential scenarios of cooperation with the private sector based on integrated EPOS RI which would include a description of the flow of legal documents and legal actions,

As part of the work on D5.6 and D5.7, an effort was also made to determine the feasibility and usefulness of describing specific scenarios for cooperation with the private sector and to prepare a description of the document flow and legal activities under such scenarios. The work on gathering the information necessary to prepare such scenarios and the preparation of descriptions was the subject of the third phase of work under WP 5.3, the result of which will be summarised in chapter 4 hereof.

In order to achieve the objectives set out above, a number of available studies commissioned by the European Commission in recent years have been analysed to identify principles for cooperation between research infrastructure and industry, including in particular deliverables prepared within the framework of ENRIITC (the European Network of Research Infrastructure and Industry for Collaboration)¹ and ESFRI (The European Strategy Forum of Research Infrastructures).² The conclusions drawn from the analysis of these studies have been superimposed on the information on the specific conditions of EPOS-integrated infrastructure in order to make specific and individualised recommendations. The above issues were also discussed in meetings with the ENRIITC representative and representatives of EPOS ERIC, with a view to defining tailored solutions that take into account the particular circumstances of the EPOS ERIC research infrastructure.

2. Analysis of the readiness of the research infrastructure integrated within EPOS to engage with the private sector

The work carried out by the members of WP5 by conducting numerous interviews and surveys obtained from EPOS stakeholders has made it possible to gather important information about existing and expected relationships with the private sector within the entities that manage the EPOS integrated research infrastructure. The results of the above work gathered especially in deliverables D5.2 - First report on EPOS-Private sector interaction and D5.3 - Second report on EPOS-Private sector interaction allowed analysis to be carried out in terms of elements having a significant impact on the possibility of creating a common legal framework. Some of the data were gathered separately during the work on deliverable D 5.6 by the way of interviews with representatives of member institutions and participation in meetings and discussion during the meetings.

The main conclusions from the analysis of the above-mentioned gathered data and information were as follows:

- I. Existing cooperation with the private sector takes place at the level of individual TCS members;

¹ <https://enriitc.eu/project/deliverables/>

² <https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-scripta-series>

- II. Only a part of direct services offered within TCS is ready for use by the private sector partners. Part of the services is not ready (in terms of technological advancement) for direct use by the private sector and is unlikely to be ready in the near future. Part of the TCS doesn't have information or tools to identify readiness to offer direct services to the private sector;
- III. General conclusion of major part of TCS members is that the cooperation with the private sector is scarce or non-existent and no clear interest has been identified from the private sector to cooperate;
- IV. In case of part of TCS there is no clear understanding of the legal chain of documents and actions pertinent to ongoing cooperation with the private sector;
- V. There are widely divergent views on the role of and, how to use particular legal instruments for regulating cooperation with the private sector.

The above information allows to conclude that within the EPOS structure, there has been no coherent dialogue to date on the possibilities and mechanisms for cooperation with the private sector, resulting in the absence of what we might call a common legal and organisational culture for cooperation with the private sector. Such a culture would be a first step toward creation of the coherent common legal framework for cooperation with the private sector. It seems, therefore, that the first and primary role of EPOS ERIC is to take steps that will lead to the creation of such a culture, i.e., a space for a common dialogue on organisational and legal solutions. Numerous meetings initiated as part of the work of the various EPOS SP project groups have laid the groundwork for such a dialogue within the EPOS community. The above occasion highlighted the usefulness of having such a community dialogue in a permanent system.

It should also be deduced from the analysis of the above information that the creation of a common space for dialogue and therefore a common legal and organisational culture should be steered centrally and therefore from the level of EPOS ERIC and not from the level of distributed infrastructures (TCS) or individual member organizations, despite of the fact that any actual contracting with the private sector concerning the provision of specific services will predominantly take place at the level of individual TCS members - private sector, rather than at the level of EPOS - private sector.

On the basis of the material collected, the following conclusion also emerges, EPOS is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure, which makes the dialog with the industry difficult. On the other side, the multidisciplinary infrastructure and the involved TCS have the potential to develop collaboration with the industry based on multidisciplinary integrated data and services. In D5.4 was identified that efforts should be made to gain the interest of the private sector targeting users that may be interested in multidisciplinary integrated data/data products and services. **The issue of the potential possibility of multidisciplinary projects seems to be a distinguishing feature of the EPOS community and, thus, may account for its attractiveness to the private sector.** However, the possibility of initiating and coordinating of collaboration with the aspect of multidisciplinary, presupposes the need to initiate and coordinate such projects at the EPOS ERIC level.

An important suggestion made in D5.4 that when working with industry EPOS should consider also the case when the private sector is an indirect user (e.g., through **scientists acting as consultants**). This idea was further developed during the meetings with the ENRIITC representative and the group came out with the suggestion that offering the support of experts shall be a service organized and available on the level of EPOS ERIC.

The general conclusion was that there is little interest of the private sector in the data and services aggregated in TCS and it is not likely that this will be the important area for cooperation with the private sector in the future. However, the possible interaction with the industry as a partner is very important. In this case EPOS capacity to offer services for open innovation should be considered.

The promising potential for realising collaborations with the private sector is therefore not so much the integrated research infrastructure itself, but the community organised around this infrastructure. Up-to-date and high-quality research infrastructure lends credibility to this community

3. Recommendations from WP5 on EPOS-Private Sector interaction

3.1 The role of EPOS ERIC as a brokering institution

One of the results from the analysis in the D5.5 and the D5.6 is about the important role of EPOS ERIC as a brokering institution. This role may be seen in the perspective of the communication strategy, that is a role in providing dissemination and promotion and giving credibility and strengthening the position of the scientific entities operating within EPOS as important partners for the private sector. However, the role of EPOS ERIC as a brokering institution may be equally important in the field of setting legal and organisational framework, that is taking steps toward creating a common legal and organisational culture in cooperating with the private sector. It has to be mentioned that assigning of such a role to the centralised organization within the integrated research infrastructure has been indicated as an important factor for stimulating innovation. **Therefore, it is highly recommended that there is an Industry Liaison Officer position or office established on the level of EPOS ERIC, to which the brokering functions are entrusted.**

It is important to stipulate that the functions of such a person, or office, must be defined taking into account the limitations arising directly from the content of the EPOS ERIC Statutes. In accordance with art. 3 section 3 of Statutes of the European Plate Observing System — European Research Infrastructure Consortium (EPOS ERIC) C/2018/7011:

*EPOS ERIC shall pursue its principal task on a non-economic basis. EPOS ERIC **may carry out limited economic activities, provided that they are closely related to its principal task and that they do not jeopardise the achievement thereof.***

The principal task of the EPOS ERIC is (art. 3 section 1 of Statutes) *to establish and operate the distributed European Plate Observing System and to provide an effective governance framework to drive the integration and coordination of the Thematic Core Services (TCS) and build and provide governance for the Integrated Core Services (ICS).*

The above regulations do not in any way preclude EPOS ERIC from establishing a centralized Industry Contact Officer or Office (further on as “ICO”), as far as the main objectives of the work of such a body are properly defined so that its activities remain consistent with the fulfilment of the statutory objectives by the EPOS ERIC.

In the view of the above, the main objectives for the activity of ILO should be:

- promoting cooperation with the private sector that is geared towards **stimulating innovation**,
- creating cooperation with the private sector to achieve **sustainability** of the integrated infrastructure

The most important recommendations regarding the activities and functions of the central ILO within EPOS ERIC will be presented below. The recommendations will be presented from the perspective of the impact of such a body on the organizational and legal framework for cooperation with the private sector. Its possible functions in terms of communication strategy are a subject of studies prepared under other deliverables.

A. Creation of a permanent structure

In our view, the ILO should operate as a permanent position or an office with permanent staff (including at least one full-time staff). One of the significant problems observed in the work on the legal framework is the fragmentation of the dialogue due to the lack of an entity/person to sustain the dialogue between the dispersed meetings of those involved in substantive work within the TCS. The lack of continuity combined with the considerable spatial dispersion of those involved in the work of the TCS results in a lack of space to gather consistent and continuous information and conclusions on relevant aspects of cooperation with the private sector.

B. Introduce structured methods for describing the infrastructure collected within EPOS ERIC in a way that facilitates the regulation of cooperation with the private sector.

The following aspects should be taken into account:

- the ownership structure of the infrastructure,
- the basic characteristics of the collected infrastructure,
- the type of services provided,
- the legal instruments implemented (type of licences, etc.).

Gathering this information in one place and structuring it according to common rules will not only facilitate the creation of an advanced legal framework but will also be an important knowledge base for private parties interested in cooperation.

C. Mapping of information on existing cooperation with the private sector in all TCS with information on legal solutions adopted

A structured description of existing relationships can form the basis for copying or correcting existing practices and exploring sources of innovation-based partnerships.

D. Recommending technical and communication solutions aimed at obtaining up-to-date information on the interest of the private sector in the services offered in TCS

Knowing the real current interest can help to develop services, adapt legal tools, and work on specific collaborative offers based on innovation.

E. Creation of a database of use cases (success stories) of cooperation with the private sector including innovative projects

Structured, centrally accessible information will allow learning by example and to search for general solutions for the future.

In our view, it is only with the introduction of the above solutions that it will be possible to realistically and adequately sort out at EPOS ERIC level the relevant legal areas defined under D 5.5, i.e.

- introduction of service quality control standards,
- enforcing open access rules,
- securing intellectual rights to the results,
- regulations concerning founding,
- OHS rules.

3.2 The role of EPOS as multidisciplinary infrastructure - the role of EPOS as a community

EPOS has a very important role not only as a platform but also as a community of scientists with different background and expertise. The joint efforts of the community can provide solutions not only to basic scientific problems but also for complex challenging problems that arise as a result from industrial activity. In this case the scientific community and the industry can work together as partners and the result could have a very high potential for innovation. The interaction between the EPOS community and the industry community can start with a workshop with exchange of scientific knowledge on one side and the challenging problems on the other side. A wide discussion between both communities can find which problems could be solved, what kind of specialists would be necessary to be involved, and to develop a partnership. The results can be published in scientific journal and the solutions (services developed as a result of the cooperation and possibly the data used) can be published on the EPOS platform.

The multidisciplinary character of the community can play a very important role to attract the industry and to find non-ordinary innovative solutions to industry-related problems.

In these cases, probably multiple TCS will be involved and multiple organizations within them.

3.3 Creating modern and innovative services with experts.

It was noticed that an important quality of the community around EPOS ERIC infrastructure is the fact that it allows access to specialists (experts). Expert would be a person who uses EPOS services working for industry, someone collaborating/working permanently with industry. An important service that could be organized at the level of EPOS ERIC is updated information about the experts active within each TCS and the contact point to communicate with the experts. Permanent availability of such service may enhance creation of multidisciplinary projects.

4. Description of chain of legal documents withing different lines of cooperation with PS

It follows from the analysis that three main lines of cooperation between the private sector and EPOS can be identified. It should be pointed out, as is evident from previous findings, that direct cooperation with the private sector will be established by the TCS members.

A. Upstream – private sector as a supplier

This type of cooperation can be divided into two phases: Phase I is the cooperation in the development of the key infrastructure for the operation of the EPOS resource and the provision of the necessary components to make the resource operational. This phase has been carried out in the framework of individual TCS on the basis of national law and is in principle now in its final stage. Using TCS AH as an example, it can be pointed out that the acquisition of infrastructure components from the private partner has been done on the basis of tenders.

The second phase, currently in progress, is the phase of providing services for the operation of the acquired infrastructure (in particular data and software). Within that phase licence agreements are concluded for the rights to use the services delivered in this phase. This process takes place through the conclusion of a 'package' of licence agreements, consisting of: an agreement between the original owner and the institution creating the episode or acquiring the service, an agreement between that institution and the data center owners, an agreement between the data center owners and owners of the platforms through which the data and services are made available. The data centers and the platforms used to publish data and services should be considered as crucial infrastructure within given TCS. The major part of these agreements has the character of a permanent cooperation agreement, meaning that additional services are provided on a continuous basis without the need to conclude further agreements each time.

In this phase, i.e., the phase in which the private partner acts as a provider of services (e.g. data, services, databases, software), contracts will most often be concluded at the national or regional level. Under this model, the TCS institutions which act as owners of the crucial infrastructure acquire from the private partner the resources necessary for its operation or expands the database or services available. This aspect of cooperation involves the need for the TCS to provide adequate infrastructure solutions to take over the resources from the private partner, or to provide support to the private partner at the stage of data collection or creation of services, in order to adapt the provided services to the requirements of the TCS. The cooperation here is, as a rule, unpaid and unilateral (the support of the TCS is marginal, most often consisting in the provision of appropriate procedures to enable the transfer of services).

The key legal issue in this case becomes the creation of appropriate regulations enabling the acquisition of services from the private partner in a way that does not limit the possibility of their further transfer and dissemination within EPOS and also to be used for the commercial purposes. Appropriate regulations should, in principle, be based on royalty-free, territorially and temporally unlimited licensing agreements allowing TCS to incorporate the acquired services into the EPOS infrastructure and allow them to be used by users of solutions provided within EPOS.

The basic problem resulting from the above construction is the diversity of legal systems that can be used to assess the validity and effectiveness of licence agreements. For the assessment of particular contracts, the regulations of states in which, for example, the seat of the private partner is located may apply, and these regulations may exclude or limit the possibility to construct agreements on the basis of regulations existing in international trade (e.g., Creative Commons).

An exceptionally important topic that should also be harmonised at the level of operation of the entire EPOS is the issue of responsibility for the correctness of data and the correctness of the operation of services, including the identification of the entities that bear this responsibility. In the case of services provided free of charge, as a rule, this responsibility will not be assumed by private partners.

The above issues are best safeguarded by including in contracts with data and service providers a mandate to publish the data and services with one of the widely recognised open licences, in a version that allows commercial use and in a version that does not force further open release of products created from these data and services. In the case of data, this task is fulfilled by the Common Creative licence version CC BY 4.0 and in the case of services (which are mostly software) by the Apache 2.0 Licence. Both of these licences are widely recognised and used internationally, which can exclude risks associated with different legislations that may govern various situation. Both licences allow commercial use without forcing the result to be made available on an open basis, which could discourage private users. In addition, both licences have standard limitation provisions included that exclude liability for the quality of the work.

The above issues can also be met by other licence types, but unification of licence types is also an important factor, which will be important in multidisciplinary projects that may rely on data coming from multiple providers.

B. Downstream – private sector as a user

The second field in which the interface between the private partner and EPOS occurs is when the private partner acts as a service user.

The legal issue in this situation focuses primarily on the regulation of the basis of the user's use of the services.

For the assessment of the above, it will be essential to first harmonise and structure the legal framework establishing the rules for the use of TCS services by EPOS and vice versa. Given the current legal construction of EPOS, it should be pointed out that the acquisition of services by TCS (and more specifically by the owners of the crucial infrastructure within a given TCS) does not imply an automatic acquisition of these services by EPOS. The same is true in the other direction.

It therefore becomes a prerequisite for allowing the private sector to use the services that a comprehensive regulation of the interrelationship (in terms of use of the services) between EPOS and TCS.

It is only on the basis of such a legal framework that the relationship between the private sector and EPOS can be properly established. The target model of cooperation in this field should be one in which a verified user (that is, a user who accepts the rules of use of services accessible through EPOS) has access to the resources provided to him or her, without having to request permission each time.

Under this cooperation option, it seems reasonable to consider the introduction of objective and fair criteria differentiating between users of the services, according to their need for the services and the content of EPOS' rights to the services under the concluded licence agreements.

The introduction of general regulations (e.g., rules of procedure) governing access to and use of EPOS resources by the private sector should be considered an optimal solution.

Also, to be considered is the question of payment for private partners to be able to use EPOS resources and the question of responsibility for the correctness of the services and the accuracy of the data in the resources. A fundamental problem that has not been addressed as of the date of this report is the issue of who will provide the service to the user of EPOS infrastructure (of EPOS or TCS). This problem is compounded by the lack of implementation of ICS-C, which is supposed to be a kind of hub to provide unified solutions to users.

Finally, it should be pointed out that an important issue to be regulated is the question of EPOS acquiring rights to use the results of work carried out using EPOS services.

C. Private sector as a partner

The last of the fields in which cooperation between EPOS and the private sector can occur is that in which both parties act as partners. This model implies a commitment of resources on both sides (EPOS and private partner), but also a mutual benefit from the results of such cooperation.

The partnership can occur both at the stage of acquiring services from the private sector (e.g., the private partner making its resources available to acquire data that will serve both for the development of EPOS as well as provide tangible economic value for the private partner) as well as at the stage of using data held by EPOS by the private partner (as mentioned in point 2 above, a natural field for such cooperation seems to be the possibility for EPOS to use the data obtained by the private partner and the result of a work performed on the basis of EPOS services).

The win-win partnership model appears to be the optimal model for achieving the mission and purpose of EPOS. A win-win collaboration that contributes to the development of services deserves to be prioritised.

It is legally important to regulate the contractual rules between the private sector and EPOS and to indicate at least the minimum content of the contractual clauses in order to synchronise and harmonise the rights acquired by EPOS to the results of the parties' mutual cooperation.

The harmonisation and unification of contract templates will ensure greater transparency in the actions undertaken and make it possible to ensure non-discriminatory treatment of potential private sector partners.

In summary: the above considerations suggest that one of the most important issues currently facing EPOS is the development and implementation of procedures with the long-term objective of harmonising and synchronising the acquisition of resources by EPOS from private parties and standardising the rules for the use of EPOS services, irrespective of the source of acquisition. The introduction of harmonised regulation will ensure equal and non-discriminatory access to resources and harmonise the pattern of acquisition. A key factor that may make it impossible or significantly more difficult to achieve the objective set out above is the variety of legal regimes that may apply to the EPOS-Private Partner relationship.